

VALKYRIES

D3.5 Business Cases

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of Task 3.6 of Exploitation and Commercial Deployment.

The deliverable includes a report of the different Business Cases derived from the conducted research, integrations, applications and demonstrators.

At a global level, all the identified opportunities are included in the interoperability model defined by SIGRUN (result of the D2.8 Architecture Design Document) and under this interoperability framework the different applications of the different technological partners have been adapted. The implementation of this interoperability model in technological applications gives value to the reference framework and the fact that it is used in all the demonstrators guarantees the harmonisation of the technology and procedures of the project and ensures that the defined model is feasible.

Mainly these opportunities were identified in the different deliverables of WP4/WP5 and WP6 and have been strengthened from the implementation of the first UC between Spain and Portugal and has been based on the adaptation of the different technological tools of the partners to this Valkyries model. In this first implementation in UC 1, the commercial potential of the tools, included in the technological framework defined in the Valkyries project, has already been detected.

In the following UCs, the aim is to continue improving these adaptations and adding new functionalities adjusted to the user's requirements and needs.

This deliverable is a first version as a starting point for the next deliverable. The exploitation model and the IPR will be defined in more detail in the next deliverable (D3.6. Exploitation Plan).

2. Identification

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3. Introduction

The increasing natural, human-made or pandemic emergencies are motivating the growth of the emergency management market, especially regarding the technological advancement in tools, devices and first aids vehicles used for disaster management, including enhanced communication and data exchange systems.

The first objective (OBJ-1) of the project is to map the growing commercial and Research and Development opportunities, analysing the existing/ongoing technological (WP4 working stream KARA), procedural (WP5 working stream HERJA) and education and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response (WP6 working stream EIR) supplier markets to improve the EU disaster resiliency to later translate them into business opportunities using the contemporary Business Model Canvas method of Osterwalder [1] to fast track the business modelling and commercialisation steps of the project and with continuous evaluation and advice on the ethical and legal aspects (OBJ-2).

This document satisfies partially the initial requirement REQ_COM_T6.6_3 from D2.7- Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases M12, identifying and reporting the main business opportunities detected during the project execution.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results (Tested before and during the project pilots)
REQ_COM_T3.6_3	N/A	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2	D6.5 D3.6	REQUIRED	This document identifies and reports the business opportunities from research outputs

Table 1 – Traceability Matrix

3.1. Methodology

The Business Model Canvas [2] is a strategic management tool that is to visualize and analyse the key elements of a business model. The canvas consists of nine blocks that describe the key aspects of a business, and it can be used to assess the viability and effectiveness of a business model.

This model is widely used throughout the industry and will be used as the basis for commercial exploitation of the outputs.

The nine blocks of the Business Model Canvas are:

1. Customer Segments: Identifying the different groups of people or organizations that a business aims to serve.
2. Value Proposition: Defining the unique value that a business offers to its customers and the problems it solves for them.
3. Channels: Describing how a business delivers its value proposition to its customers through various channels.
4. Customer Relationships: Outlining the types of relationships that a business establishes and maintains with its customers.
5. Revenue Streams: Identifying the ways in which a business generates revenue from its customers.

6. Key Activities: Describing the core activities that a business must perform to deliver its value proposition.
7. Key Resources: Identifying the key resources, including people, technology, and physical assets, that a business needs to operate.
8. Key Partners: Identifying the key partners, suppliers, and other stakeholders that a business works with to deliver its value proposition.
9. Cost Structure: Outlining the costs that a business incurs in order to operate and generate revenue.

Figure 1 - Business Model Canvas [3]

From the main business opportunities detected within VALKYRIES development, a Business Model Canvas is implemented giving a better understanding of how each Business Case (BC) work and how to improve the business model to create more value for customers and generate more revenue.

3.2. Business Cases summary

The following table presents the main BC detected during the project. On the next chapters The Business Model Canvas for each case will be presented.

BC ID	BC name	Origin	BC description
BC1	Tassica App for MCI	CO.WP4.42 / CO.WP5-7 / CO.WP5-13 Demonstrators	TASSICA Multi Casualty Incident (MCI) Management is an application for real-time management of medical assistance in mass casualty incidents, enabling first responders to network and share information to optimise resource management. The result is a better response and an increase in the number of lives saved.

BC ID	BC name	Origin	BC description
BC2	SIGRUN Framework	WP4 Clustered Opportunities Demonstrators	SIGRUN as a free interoperability framework
BC3	SIGRUN Reference Implementation	WP4 clustered opportunities Demonstrators	The Reference Implementation of SIGRUN allows to setup the SIGRUN interoperability framework, including the interoperability protocols among different third-party systems, authentication, authorization, account management and persistent storage systems.
BC4	VALKYRIES GLOBAL COP	CO.WP4.15 CO.WP4.16 CO.WP4.18 CO.WP4.25 CO.WP4.29 CO.WP4.42 CO.WP5.12 CO.WP5.13 Demonstrators	The VALKYRIES global Common Operational Picture (COP) provides a Common Operational Picture of incidents, involving organizations and associated assets (human resources and equipment) and victims. The VALKYRIES Global COP allows strategic and operational emergency response professionals to follow the unfolding information on incidents, including the assignment of assets to the response effort, and details on the victims, including their triage and evacuation to specific destinations, such as nearby hospitals.
BC5	Command and Control Platform iSafety	WP4 Cluster Opportunities Demonstrators	iSafety Command and Control Application implementation of interoperability model of SIGRUN

Table 2 – Business Cases summary

4. Business Case Canvas

4.1. BC1 Canvas - Tassica App for MCI

BC1 Canvas: Tassica App for MCI				
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Consultancy for adaptation and deployment into legacy systems. -Software Development and testing of new features -Online support. -Sales and Marketing. -Large software implementation company with international presence and recognized financial and technological solvency. 	<p>KEY ACTIVITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Consultancy for adaptation and deployment into legacy systems. -Software Development and testing of new features Online support. -Sales and Marketing. 	<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>TASSICA S.A. offers:</p> <p>An app as well as the corresponding adaptation of the app, if necessary, together with a consultancy and a training package.</p> <p>TASSICA App for MCI:</p> <p>Streamlines the transmission of information Improves work operations</p> <p>TASSICA App for MCI is a completely new solution in a market that currently still uses media that is unreliable and has very limited capacity for information transfer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simple IT tool that manages MULTIPLE VICTIM INCIDENT (An event which, due to the large number of patients and the nature of their injuries, means that the number of resources and healthcare personnel available are insufficient to attend to all the injured according to the usual criteria. It is therefore necessary to optimize the performance of resources as much as possible). - Facilitates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The most rigorous and effective action of the health professional. - The coordinated response of all resources, over and above the multiplicity of intervening services. - The taking of care and command decisions in such critical circumstances. 	<p>CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Direct sales to emergency management agencies and organisations. -Partnerships with system integrators and technology providers. -Online marketing and advertising, website/mobile. -Promotion at exhibitions and congresses. -After sales support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Online support/information -Open requests for feature development -Open online training for customers. -Valkyries dissemination. 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -First Responders. -Emergency management agencies and organizations. -Government Agencies. -Technology Providers for Emergency systems (Integration Companies).
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <p>Software Development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Proficient in various programming languages such as Java, C++, and Python. -Strong understanding of software development methodologies and practices. -Experience in developing and maintaining software applications for diverse platforms. <p>Data Management and Storage:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Expertise in designing and implementing data management and storage infrastructure. -Proficient in database systems, data integration, and data security. <p>Experience in the field of MCI management.</p> <p>ICT infrastructure.</p> <p>Expertise in emergency response and pre-hospital medical care.</p>		<p>CHANNELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Direct sales to emergency management agencies and organizations. -Partnerships with system integrators and technology providers. -Online marketing and advertising, website/mobile. -Promotion at exhibitions and congresses. -After sales support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online support/information -Open requests for feature development - Open online training for customers. -Valkyries dissemination. 	

BC1 Canvas: Tassica App for MCI	
COST STRUCTURE <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Software development and maintenance costs.-Sales and marketing expenses.-Customer support and training expenses.-ICT cloud services expenses.-ICT infrastructure-Integration costs.-Maintenance costs.	REVENUE STREAMS <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Revenue Generation.-Value-Added Services.-Subscription Payment Models.-Customer Relationship Management.-Platform Deployment and Maintenance.-Consultancy and Customization.-Integration with customer processes and tools.-Data Analytics and prediction of results TYPES: <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Licensing (based on volume)-Direct sales (customized solution).-Subscription model for customer services (specific payment plan for -maintenance, support and operations based on customer characteristics).-Value-added consulting services (product development and integration services)

Table 3 – BC1 Canvas: Tassica App for MCI

4.2. BC2 Canvas - SIGRUN as an interoperability framework

BC2 Canvas: SIGRUN as an interoperability Framework				
KEY PARTNERS -Technology Providers (communication Service Providers) -System Integrators and resellers for premium services (Development Providers) -Government Agencies -Data providers with Real Time Information	KEY ACTIVITIES -Online Support -Consultancy for adaptation and deployment into legacy systems -Software Development and testing of new features -Sales and Marketing Platform maintenance	VALUE PROPOSITION -Provides a framework for sharing information related to Emergency Management between different Agencies or between countries. - Free standard of the VALKYRIES framework model -Premium Services for Implementing and Customizing the platform into legacy systems, deploying in cloud and developing new features. -Additional features in a subscription-license base model (Language translation services, Encryption Module, Forensics Module, GDPR adaptation) -CHARACTERISTICS -Customization -Interoperability -Easy to implement -Accessibility -Cost (low-cost solution) -Scalable Solution.	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP -Collaboration with costumers on customizing Platform and configurations -Continuous improvement based on customer feedback and industry Best Practices	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS -First Responders -Emergency management agencies and organizations -Government Agencies -Technology Providers for Emergency systems (Integration Companies)
	KEY RESOURCES -Software Development Team -Partnership with Emergency management agencies and organizations		CHANNELS -Website and online community for downloads, documentation, support, and potential usage. -Direct Sales for premium services to Emergency management agencies and organizations -Partnerships with local system integrators and resellers -Online marketing and advertising -Specific channels for premium services (each partner can provide a specific service) -Valkryies Dissemination	
COST STRUCTURE -Development costs, maintenance and support, infrastructure and marketing efforts and community Support		REVENUE STREAMS -Additional revenue for value - added services related to the platform (Consultancy, implementation, deployment, maintenance) -Additional revenue for value- services in the core Platform (Translation Service, GIS Module, Dashboards module)		

Table 4 – BC2 Canvas: SIGRUN as an interoperability framework

4.3. BC3 Canvas- Reference Implementation of SIGRUN

BC3 Canvas: Reference Implementation of SIGRUN				
KEY PARTNERS - VALKYRIES partners. - Emergency Response Organizations. - Emergency Management Bodies. - Civil protection and public safety and security authorities.	KEY ACTIVITIES - Design. - Adaptation and customization. - System integration. - Support & Operations. - R&D and Innovation. - Consulting services.	VALUE PROPOSITION The Reference Implementation of SIGRUN facilitates the exchange of information between different third-party systems so that cross-organization coordination and management is efficient, cost-effective and performed in near real-time to the benefit of joint emergency response efforts.	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP -Sales force. -Website and social media platforms; ---- -Training materials and manuals. -Hands-on Workshops. Pitch Events. - Customer and partner networks.	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS -Emergency Response --Organizations. -Emergency Management Bodies. -Civil protection and public safety and security authorities.
	KEY RESOURCES - Field expertise - ICT Infrastructure - Computing resources - Best practices in joint emergency response.		CHANNELS -Customer and partner networks. -Website and social media platforms. -Public and private emergency response networks. -Emergency Response -- Organizations (word of mouth) -Marketing and advertising events.	
COST STRUCTURE - ICT Infrastructure. - Cloud ICT Services. - Research and development. - Integration. - Maintenance. - Sales. - Marketing and advertising. - Internal training.			REVENUE STREAMS - <i>Licensing</i> - <i>Services development</i>	

Table 5 – BC3 Canvas: Reference Implementation of SIGRUN

4.4. BC4 Canvas- Valkyries GLOBAL COP

BC4 Canvas: Valkyries GLOBAL COP				
KEY PARTNERS - VALKYRIES partners. - Emergency Response Organizations. - Emergency Management Bodies. - Civil protection and public safety and security authorities.	KEY ACTIVITIES - Design. - Adaptation and customization. - System integration. - Support & Operations. - R&D and Innovation. - Consulting services.	VALUE PROPOSITION Provides a user-friendly and intuitive global overview of incidents and involved assets, enabling the sharing of the information between the organizations involved in the response effort. Incident commanders and managers are able to visualize the geo-referenced overview of incidents, their assigned assets and the status of incident and asset; medical response organizations have a full situational awareness of the status of the victims' triage process, up to their evacuation to specific destinations, such as nearby hospitals. The real-time Global COP System supports the efficient management of incident response and of the resources and assets assigned and deployed to the field, as well as of pre-hospital assistance in the context of large-incident response, improving the quality of the response effort	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP - Sales force. - Website and social media platforms. - Training materials and manuals. - Hands-on Workshops. - Pitch Events. - Customer and partner networks.	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS - Emergency Response Organizations. - Emergency Management Bodies. - Civil protection and public safety and security authorities.
	KEY RESOURCES - Field expertise - ICT Infrastructure - Computing resources - Best practices in emergency response and pre-hospital medical assistance.		CHANNELS - Customer and partner networks. - Website and social media platforms. - Public and private emergency response networks.	
COST STRUCTURE - ICT Infrastructure. - Cloud ICT Services. - Research and development. - Integration. - Maintenance. - Sales. - Marketing and advertising. - Internal training.			REVENUE STREAMS - Direct sales (customized solution) - Subscription model for customer services (dedicated payment plan on maintenance, customer support and operation, based on customer characteristics) - Pay-per-use (web access) - Added-value consultancy services (product evolution and integration services); - Licensing.	

Table 6 – BC4 Canvas: Valkyries GLOBAL COP

4.5. BC5 Canvas - iSafety as a Command-and-Control tool implemented into SIGRUN Framework

BC5 Canvas: iSafety as a Command and Control				
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - VALKYRIES partners. - Emergency Response Organizations. - Emergency Management Bodies. - Civil protection and public safety and security authorities. 	<p>KEY ACTIVITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Software Development and customization of iSafety. -Software development and integration of Digital Twins technology -Continuous improvement based on customer feedback and emerging technologies Sales and marketing -Customer support and training - Deployment and Maintenance 	<p>VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>iSafety is a Command-and-Control tool for emergency management that is integrated in the SIGRUN reference model and with the rest of the applications of the other partners (GLOBAL COP by Particle and Tassica MCI App). This integration has improved the interoperability of the tool and increases the possibilities of integration with other third-party systems.</p> <p>Additionally, the integration of INDRA's Digital Twins tools (HTL) allows the creation of virtual scenarios that improve emergency management.</p> <p>Some of the most relevant functionalities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Real-time situational awareness and decision support with integrated Digital Twins technology -Enhanced incident response through virtual representation and simulation of physical assets and environments -Improved resource allocation and coordination during emergencies 	<p>CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Personalized customer support and training -Collaboration with customers on customizing Command and Control Tool and Digital Twins configurations and workflows -Continuous improvement based on customer feedback and industry best practices -Proactive monitoring and maintenance of Isafety and Digital Twins Platform 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Emergency management agencies and organizations -First Responders

BC5 Canvas: iSafety as a Command and Control			
	<p>KEY RESOURCES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Software development team specialized in Emergency Protocols development. -Software development team specialized in Digital Twins technology -Data management and storage infrastructure for Digital Twins -Partnerships with emergency management agencies and organizations -Intellectual property related to Digital Twins technology 	<p>Interoperability model of SIGRUN</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Customizable incident management workflows and reporting -Capabilities Integration with existing emergency management systems and communication channels 	<p>CHANNELS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Direct sales to emergency management agencies and organizations -Partnerships with system integrators and technology providers -Online marketing and advertising -Valkyries Dissemination
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Software development and maintenance costs - Infrastructure costs for Digital Twins data management and storage - Sales and marketing expenses 		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Subscription fees based on number of users and incidents managed - Implementation and customization fees for enterprise customers - Additional revenue from value-added services (e.g., data analytics, predictive modeling) 	

Table 7 – BC5 Canvas: iSafety as a Command and Control

5. Conclusions

In this first phase, 5 business opportunities have been identified. They are mainly articulated according to the SIGRUN reference model and have been developed according to the technological capabilities of each partner in the project, adapting the tools available at the beginning of the project based on the business opportunities detected.

In the analysis of the business cases, we have differentiated the SIGRUN framework, which is the common design part with its own business model, from the SIGRUN implementation part, which has been carried out by one of the technological partners.

From the opportunities analyses, we remarked that there are many synergies in terms of the type of customer's segments and services we can offer as a consortium. Thus, we are interested in adding as many technology partners as possible who adopt the reference model defined in SIGRUN.

We can provide a command-and-control module with the SIGRUN model together with the applications provided by Tassica and Particle or if the user already has a command-and-control tool, we can offer the services of adapting the SIGRUN model to incorporate legacy applications and implement the integration of the Tassica app and the GLOBAL COP of Particle, for example. SIGRUN acts as an ecosystem of integrated applications and services. We can also offer services related to training and consultancy as well.

Based on this model, the IPR model, the adequacy of the background and exploitation for each use case must continue to be analysed and it is likely that some adaptation will be made in the rest of the Use Cases (UC). To date, only UC#1 between Spain and Portugal has been executed and this document reflects the opportunities detected mainly in this UC.

6. Annex A – References and bibliography

6.1. Internal references

1. VALKYRIES D2.2 - Terminology and semantics
2. VALKYRIES D2.7 – Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases
3. VALKYRIES D4.3 - Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European technological capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
4. VALKYRIES D5.3 - Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European operational and procedural capabilities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters
5. VALKYRIES D6.3 - Roadmap for enhancing the pan-European preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters

6.2. External references

- [1] A. Osterwalder, Y. Pigneur and C. Tucci, “Clarifying Business Models: Origins, Present, and Future of the Concept,” 2005. [Online]. Available: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/cais/vol16/iss1/1/>.
- [2] A. Osterwalder, The Business Model Ontology - A Proposition in a Design Science Approach, 2004.
- [3] “<https://www.garyfox.co/canvas-models/how-to-use-business-model-canvas-guide>,” [Online]. [Accessed 2023].

7. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
BC	Business Case
COP	Command Operational Picture
MCI	Multi Casualty Incident
UC	Use Case

Table 8 – Glossary